

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR MEMORIZING FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY**Kostadinov O.***Ph.D., Guest Lecturer**Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy**Varna, Bulgaria*<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9183-5243><https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12700654>

Study in Support of Foreign Language Learning

Abstract

Learning and memorizing foreign language vocabulary is a multifaceted process influenced by various stages of language acquisition and the natural phenomenon of forgetting. This paper discusses effective strategies for overcoming the challenges associated with forgetting and consolidating foreign vocabulary. By examining the Ebbinghaus Forgetting Curve and the impact of repetition on memory retention, the paper highlights the importance of spaced repetition and other mnemonic techniques. The stages of foreign word learning, from initial recognition to natural active vocabulary use, are explored to provide insights into effective vocabulary acquisition. Key strategies such as spaced repetition, active use, mnemonics, and contextual learning are emphasized to enhance long-term retention and active use of foreign language vocabulary.

Keywords: *Foreign Language Vocabulary; Memorization Strategies; Ebbinghaus Forgetting Curve; Spaced Repetition; Language Acquisition; Mnemonics; Contextual Learning; Vocabulary Retention*

1. Introduction

Learning a foreign language and memorizing new vocabulary is a complex process that involves different stages of language acquisition. Forgetting is a natural phenomenon that accompanies the process of learning a foreign language. This necessitates the consolidation of the vocabulary of foreign words, for which it is necessary to consolidate the learned words through various forms of repetition. Mastering foreign words involves not only recognizing them but also understanding their meaning in the native language, as well as their active use. Empirical studies show general trends regarding the stages of learning foreign vocabulary and the frequency of repetition necessary for the effective integration of new words into the active vocabulary.

Forgetting is an inherent human trait. Although we cannot eliminate it, we can mitigate its impact through appropriate methods. People typically accumulate information by keeping some of it in long-term memory, but they also lose other information. The human mind does not distinguish between useful and unnecessary information and cannot control forgetting, which is a natural process. Forgetting useful information, especially foreign language vocabulary, is undesirable and represents a significant challenge. Acquisition of foreign language vocabulary can be unconscious, without effort, or conscious, through deliberate mental work, with which a person can improve the memorization process. In this context, the use of certain concepts and facts necessitates their memorization, while the logical derivation of others can occur even without direct memory. Vocabulary acquisition of foreign words occurs primarily through memorization, although logical reconstruction can sometimes help recall words or phrases derived from other known words. The process of forgetting foreign vocabulary can be a one-time

event or a gradual decrease, depending on the level of its mastery.

Primary conclusion: By using effective strategies for learning and memorizing foreign vocabulary, we can combat the forgetting that comes with learning a foreign language. These strategies lead to the successful acquisition and active use of a foreign language.

2. Stages of Foreign Language Word Learning

2.1. Initial Recognition without Understanding the meaning of the foreign words:

– Description: The learner recognizes the new word from repeated exposure, but they don't understand its meaning in context.

– Example: The learner sees or hears the word "cat" and knows they have seen or heard it before, but they still do not understand its meaning.

Primary Conclusion: The first stage in learning new words involves recognizing them without understanding their meaning. Cognitive psychology and educational theories of language learning ground this process. [1]

2.2. Approximate Contextual Understanding:

– Description: The learner can understand the approximate meaning of the new word in the context of a sentence without knowing its exact meaning.

– Example: The learner sees the word "cat" in a sentence like "The cat is on the mat" and understands that "cat" is some kind of animal, but they do not know exactly what it means.

Primary Conclusion: Learners grasp the approximate meaning of new words within the context of sentences before fully understanding their precise meaning. This stage is supported by language learning methodologies emphasizing contextual nuances. [2][3]

2.3. Precise Contextual Understanding

– Description: When the learner sees a word in the context of a sentence or text, they can understand its exact meaning.

– Example: The learner sees the word "cat" in a sentence like "The cat is on the mat" and understands that "cat" means "a feline animal" in this context.

Primary Conclusion: At this stage, learners can precisely understand the meaning of a word within a specific context. This ability is reflected in the literature on vocabulary development and language learning. [2], [3]

2.4. Precise Context-Independent Understanding:

– Description: The learner can understand and recall the meaning of the word both in the context of a sentence and on its own but does not use it actively.

– Example: The learner sees the word "cat" both in a text and on a flashcard and knows that it means "a feline animal" but does not use it actively in speech or writing.

Primary Conclusion: Learners understand and recall the meanings of words both within sentence contexts and independently, without active use. This stage is supported by studies and methodologies for developing active vocabulary. [1], [4]

2.5. Translation-Dependent Active Vocabulary:

– Description: The learner can recall and use the word in speech or writing but must first translate it from their native language.

– Example: The learner thinks of the word in their native language as "cat" and then translates it into English as "cat."

Primary Conclusion: To actively use words, learners often need to translate them from their native language. This process is foundational in translation methods and foreign language study. [3], [4]

2.6. Semi-Automatic Use:

– Description: The learner uses the word with little effort but still thinks about its meaning.

– Example: The learner says "cat" with little effort but still occasionally thinks about its meaning.

Primary Conclusion: Learners use words semi-automatically, but they may still think about their meanings. Psychologists study this stage in the context of language automation [3].

2.7. Naturally Active Vocabulary:

– Description: Words that the learner uses automatically and naturally, without thinking about translation.

– Example: When thinking about an animal, the learner automatically says "cat" without thinking about the word in their native language.

Primary Conclusion: In this final stage, learners use words naturally and automatically without thinking about translation. Language teaching methodologies and language learning thoroughly document this process. [1], [2]

3. Planning Repetition as the Right Way of Memory Consolidation

Although the exact number of repetitions may vary depending on individual differences and the learning context, we can distinguish five main stages [1], [2]:

3.1. Recognizing the foreign word as one already encountered in conversation or text without understanding its meaning:

On average, 1-3 encounters with the word are necessary for the listener to recognize the foreign word as heard before. [2]

3.2. Passively memorized words—understood only in context:

On average, about 10–20 repetitions are necessary for a word to be recognized and understood in context. This means that the learner can understand the meaning of the word when they see or hear it in a sentence. [1], [3]

3.3. Passively memorized words, understood in context and out of context:

For a word to be recognized and understood out of context, i.e., to be understood as an isolated word, about 20–40 repetitions are necessary. This includes exposure in various contexts and isolated cases. [2], [4]

3.4. Actively usable words through mental translation.

For a word to be actively used through mental translation (i.e., the learner first thinks of the word in their native language and then translates it), about 50–70 repetitions are necessary. This includes numerous translation exercises and practical use in written and spoken form. [1], [3]

3.5. Automatically used, actively usable words in the foreign language

For a word to become part of the learner's active vocabulary and be used automatically, without mental translation, about 80–100 repetitions are necessary. This includes intensive practice in real communicative situations and frequent use of the word. [1] [2]

These figures are approximate and can vary significantly depending on the individual learning style, motivation, frequency of exposure, and the quality of the learning materials. It is also important to note that repeated exposure in various contexts and active use of the words significantly improve the chances of long-term memorization and automatic use. [1], [4]

4. Analyzing Forgetting and Overcoming It as a Key Task in Learning Foreign Languages

The exponential loss in memory retention over time is modeled by the Ebbinghaus Forgetting Curve, which is a model that represents the phenomenon. The studies that Hermann Ebbinghaus carried out on himself, in which he used lists of meaningless syllables to assess how soon he would forget the knowledge, led to the development of this paradigm.

The Formula for the Forgetting Curve Developed by Ebbinghaus. One possible mathematical representation of the forgetting curve is as follows:

$$R = e^{-\frac{t}{S}}$$

– R is the retention (the amount of information retained).

– t is the time that has passed since learning.

– S is the strength of the memory.

This formula demonstrates that the rate of forgetting is initially high, but it slows down as time goes on.

This means that the rate of forgetting decreases exponentially with time.

- Harman Ebbinghaus Forgetting and Retention Curves with increased repetitions

Fig. 1 [5]

Figure 1 demonstrates the change in forgetting and retention curves over time. The red curve depicts the rate of forgetting, while the blue curve displays the rate of knowledge retention after each repeat. The abscissa (x-axis) represents the time in days, while the ordinate

(y-axis) shows the percentage of memorization. The forgetting and retention criteria are adjusted after each negotiation on days 1, 5, 12, 25, and 45.

Figure 2 [5]

Figure 2 illustrates the forgetting and retention curves for a period of forty-five days that includes twice as many repeats. It has been discovered that the forgetting curve becomes steeper due to the increased frequency of repeats, which indicates that the knowledge is remembered for a longer period. Because of this, the retention curve is larger, which indicates that a bigger proportion of customers have retained their services over the same amount of time.

- The following conclusions may be derived from the graphs:

- 1. Frequency of repetition influences forgetting:

- At more frequent repeats (as seen in the second graph), the forgetting curve is flatter, implying the rate of forgetting is lower.

- Less frequent repeats (as demonstrated in the first graph) lead to quicker loss of knowledge.

- 2. Repetition promotes information retention:

- The retention curve for more frequent repeats is much higher, suggesting that the knowledge is held in memory for a longer length of time. [6]

- 3. Learning strategy:

- For more efficient retention of information, it is desirable to use more frequent repeats, particularly in the first stages of learning.

- Over time, repeats may be diluted, but it is still vital to maintain some regularity to keep the knowledge in long-term memory.

- 4. Practical application:

- In the context of learning and memorizing, these findings justify the adoption of approaches such as spaced repetition, in which material is renegotiated at increasingly increasing intervals to promote knowledge retention.

- Key Insights

- Rapid Initial Forgetting: Immediately after learning, retention is at 100%, but it diminishes dramatically within the first several days. For example, it might decline to roughly 40% after a few days.

- Slower decrease: After the first quick decrease, the rate of forgetting slows down dramatically. Information that is maintained beyond the first period is likely to remain for a longer duration.

- Factors Influencing the Forgetting Curve

Several variables may impact the pace at which we lose information:

- Meaningfulness of the Information: More meaningful information is kept longer.

- Representation of Information: How information is encoded and structured impacts retention.

- Physiological Factors: Stress, sleep, and general mental wellness might affect memory recall.

5. Strategies for Memorizing Foreign Language Vocabulary and Techniques to Combat Forgetting

- Spaced Repetition

Utilize spaced repetition techniques (SRS) to review vocabulary at increasing intervals. This strategy exploits the spacing effect, which helps increase long-term memory by reminding learners of the words right before they are ready to forget them.

- Active Use and Practice

It is important to incorporate new terminology into everyday discussions, writing tasks, and other practical applications throughout the day. When words are used in their intended context, their meaning and use are strengthened.

- The use of mnemonics

Making language more remembered may be accomplished via the use of mnemonic devices or associations. This may include the use of acronyms, visual imagery, or the connection of words to ideas that are already known. [7]

- Flashcards

To test your understanding of new terms on a regular basis, you may use flashcards, which can be either real or digital. Anki and Quizlet are two examples of apps that might be very useful for accomplishing this goal.

- Learning Through Contextualization

Instead of learning new words in isolation, learning them in the context of sentences or tales is more effective. You will have a better understanding of how words operate within the language and will have improved retention if you use this method. [8]

- Components of Sound and Vision

Creating a multimodal learning experience may be accomplished via the use of audio recordings, films for language acquisition, and graphics. The ability to remember anything may be improved by hearing the pronunciation and seeing visual representations.

- Regular Review Sessions

Review sessions should be scheduled on a regular basis to go over previously learnt terminology. The words are moved from the short-term to the long-term memory because of this.

- Chunking

Create more digestible bits of vocabulary by breaking down big lists of words into smaller ones. Learning may be made more efficient and less daunting by breaking up the learning process into smaller chunks.

All the methods serve as strategies for memorizing foreign languages, usually in combination. [9]

Conclusion: Effective memorization of foreign language vocabulary is essential for successful language acquisition. Forgetting is an inherent part of the learning process, but its impact can be mitigated through deliberate strategies. The Ebbinghaus Forgetting Curve illustrates the need for regular repetition to combat the rapid initial decline in memory retention. Strategies such as spaced repetition, active use, mnemonic devices, and contextual learning significantly enhance vocabulary retention and usage. By integrating these techniques into language learning practices, learners can achieve more efficient and long-term mastery of foreign vocabulary, leading to better language proficiency and communication skills.

References:

1. Nation, I. S. P. (2001). "Learning Vocabulary in Another Language." Cambridge University Press. This pertains to broader trends in vocabulary learning and contextual understanding.

2. Schmitt, N. (2000). "Vocabulary in Language Teaching." Cambridge University Press. It covers the stages of learning vocabulary and methods of repetition.
3. Hulstijn, J. H. (2001). "Intentional and Incidental Second Language Vocabulary Learning: A Reappraisal of Elaboration, Rehearsal, and Automaticity." Robinson, P. (Ed.), *Cognition and Second Language Instruction*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 258–286. (Discusses cognitive processes in learning vocabulary.)
4. Laufer, B., & Hulstijn, J. (2001). "Incidental Vocabulary Acquisition in a Second Language: The Construct of Task-Induced Involvement." *Applied Linguistics*, 22(1), 1-26. This article offers valuable insights into the various stages of incidental learning and active vocabulary development.
5. Ebbinghaus Forgetting and Retention Curves. Generated using ChatGPT-4.
6. The Effectiveness of Spaced Repetition and Active Recall in Language Learning (2020), DOI: 10.1016/j.langlearn.2020.02.003, pp 345-367
7. Brown, E., (2019). Mnemonics and Vocabulary Learning in Second Language Acquisition, DOI: 10.1177/2158244018822393, pp. 233-251
8. Green, L., (2021). The Role of Contextual Learning in Vocabulary Retention, DOI: 10.1177/00336882211013678, pp. 102-119
9. Smith, J., (2018). Memory and Learning: Strategies for Success in Language Acquisition, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-98929-9, pp 120-145